

Polymethylmethacrylate-palladium composites as promising packaging material

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ABSTRACT: Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is a well-established transparent thermoplastic polymer chosen for a numerous variety of applications due to its biocompatibility, recyclability, lightweight more than glass and less expensive than it.

This study is focused on the manufacturing of a composite consisting of PMMA matrix and palladium (Pd) nanopowder in different concentrations. The obtained composite is proposed as a promising material for packaging in view of the claimed good processability, recyclability and biocompatibility of PMMA and Pd. Analyses have been conducted to evaluate the alteration of the optical clarity and wettability of the composites.

The UV-Vis spectroscopy indicated that the transmittance of the composite containing 1% and 5% Pd in the visible region decreased by about 62% and 97% respectively with respect to the pristine polymer. The quality of the dispersion of the filler was confirmed by Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier-Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) pointing to a progressive decrease of the contribution of the functional groups with the increase of the filler concentration. The modification of the wettability followed by the sessile drop method revealed a reduction of the hydrophilicity which is desirable in packaging applications to reduce the risk of contamination.

Keywords: PMMA, Pd, optical spectroscopy, surface characterization.

1.Introduction

In the 1920s, Staudinger, introduced the concept of macromolecules consisting of a large number of repeating units and received the Nobel Prize in 1953 [1]. Since then, polymer science has become a new discipline dealing with, natural and synthetic fibers, rubbers, and coatings, to name a few. Nowadays polymers have versatile uses from packaging food, and water bottles to clothing. The unreasonable use of plastic has a direct impact on the general environment and consequently hazardous effects on humans, animals and plants. United Nations mentioned the wastage of 931 million tons of food in 2019. Taking into account that over 690 million people don't have enough food to survive, the amount of waste is shameful [2]. The present conditions require the production of biodegradable or recyclable plastic with the aim of reducing CO₂ emissions as well as the dreadful amount of disposed waste.

Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is a synthetic resin produced from the polymerization of methyl methacrylate. It is a transparent and rigid plastic, extremely biocompatible, non-biodegradable, but

100% recyclable. Our study is devoted to the production of polymeric recyclable material for the development of fundamental studies and simultaneously for commercial applications in packaging material. Typically, the use of nanoparticles or structures embedded in polymeric material [3-4] are used to functionalize the existing material improving their flexibility, optical properties [5], electrical conductivity [6], chemical inertness and large surface area-to-volume ratio. The native transparency of PMMA was maintained as much as possible to facilitate the clear identification of the packaged product and at the same time, its native optical feature against external influences like UV and humidity was improved to prolong the durability and safety of the wrapped food. The production of composites of PMMA containing different concentrations of biocompatible and recyclable metallic filler like palladium has been accomplished to prove the performance of the manufactured material in the packaging branch to maintain the food quality and consequently the reduction of food spoiling.

PMMA can be processed by ion beams to produce three-dimensional (3D) micro-structures [7] and can be degraded by high-dose UV radiations [8]. PMMA can be doped by different types of atoms and molecules. A particular interest is devoted to Pd doping because it produces excellent optical fibers sensitive to hydrogen [9], changes the polymer properties such as the morphological, thermomechanical, and thermal properties [10] and changes the resistance to oxidation and dechlorination reactivity [11].

PMMA can be used as a biomaterial for many applications [12].

The aim of this investigation is to study the manufacturing of a new composite consisting of PMMA matrix and palladium filler nanopowder in different concentrations. The obtained composite is proposed as a promising material for the packaging of different substances, inorganic and organic, such as food and drugs, in view of the claimed good processability, recyclability and biocompatibility of PMMA and Pd.

2. Material and methods

PMMA is an amorphous thermoplastic polymer made up of methyl methacrylate with the monomer composition $(C_5O_2H_8)_n$, has a density of 1.19 g/cm^3 , is an insulator electrically, thermally and acoustically. It is transparent to visible light with about 93% transmissivity, is transparent to IR radiation up to about 2800 nm wavelength, has a glass transition temperature of approximately $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and has excellent mechanical resistance.

Pd is a metal with a melting point of $1554 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a boiling point of $2970 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. It is malleable and ductile, at room temperature is strongly resistant to corrosion in air and to the action of acids (except nitric acid). It has a density of 12 g/cm^3 .

PMMA powder with a particle size of 600 nm in chloroform has been blended with Palladium (Pd) nanopowder ($<25 \text{ nm}$) and $> 99.6\%$ purity was purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The obtained solution was stirred overnight at 20°C and then 10 mL of the solution was poured onto a polyethylene disc and spin-coated at 7000 rpm for 60 sec using a SPIN150i-NPP (SPS Europe B.V., TS Putten, The Netherlands). The final obtained foil (see **Figure 1**) was uniform and with a thickness of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The pristine PMMA foil was manufactured using the same procedure without the addition of Pd powder. The thickness of the PMMA film of about $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and of the PMMA+Pd of about $20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ were determined by a contact tabletop system.

Figure 1. Spin coating system a) and manufactured foils b),

The quality of the dispersion of the filler and the optical properties of the *pristine* PMMA and PMMA composites were examined by measuring their optical transmittance in the wavelength range between 200 nm and 850 nm. The UV-VIS analysis was performed using a JASCO-600 spectrophotometer.

On the other hands, the chemical composition of the composites was investigated through Attenuated Total Reflection Fourier-Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) measurements using a JASCO 7600 spectrometer.

The wettability of the samples was evaluated by the sessile drop method using an optical microscope [13]. The surface wettability is estimated by the geometrical measure of the angle formed by the intersection of the liquid at the solid, liquid, gas-phase boundary formed when a drop of liquid is placed on the surface of the sample of interest [14]. A microliter syringe (Hamilton) was used to pour a 3 μ l droplet of deionized water on the sample surface to measure the contact angle using a Paralux optical microscopy. The measure of the contact angle at the liquid/solid interface and the liquid/air interface was repeated 10 times in different areas on the sample to obtain an average standard deviation value. The measures have been repeated to overcome issues related to possible fluctuations due to changes in temperature and pressure or the non-uniformity of the samples.

A further measurement has been performed to prove the improvements in the mechanical features of the prepared composites. The shore test D is a static mechanical analysis routinely used to measure the hardness of plastic and rubber materials. The hardness (Shore D) of the samples was measured according to ASTM D2240 [15].

3. Results

The ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (see **Figure 2**) has been used to investigate the structural changes in the composites compared to the original matrix. The changes suffered by material at the molecular level can be investigated by observing the shape, intensity and position of vibrational bands [16].

Figure 2. FTIR spectrum for pristine PMMA, PMMA+1%Pd and PMMA+5%Pd foils

The intensity and position are characterized by absorptions within the functional groups of organic compounds [17]. In **Figure 2**, the strong band appearing at around 1730 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C=O stretching vibration modes of the carbonyl group [16]. The change in the intensity of the carbonyl peaks is connected to different reaction times during the acylation process [18] mediated by the chloroform. A longer reaction time produces a higher carbonyl peak intensity, indicating that the acylation process decreases in PMMA+5%Pd as the reaction time due to the presence of a higher percentage of Pd in the solutions of PMMA and Chloroform in air [19].

The band at 1730 cm^{-1} with slightly lesser intensity and slightly wider is presented in the PMMA+5%Pd composite film due to the influence of C = O. The C–H bending bands in the FTIR are located at $950\text{--}481\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [20]. The –CH stretching caused the 2942 cm^{-1} peak. The carboxylic acid groups (COOH) are responsible for the peak at 2839 cm^{-1} peak [21] is visible also in the composites although the intensity quite decreased. The N–H stretching vibration typical of the PMMA band is at 3433 cm^{-1} band [22] exhibited a strong decrease in PMMA+1%Pd while in PMMA+5%Pd it disappears. Maybe the decrease in the band intensity is due to the miscibility of PMMA and Pd filler [23].

Figure 3 compares the optical transmittance of pristine PMMA with the PMMA+Pd composites. It can be clearly seen that there is a sharp transmission decrease below 240 nm ,

corresponding to the π - π^* transition of PMMA carbonyl groups [24]. The transmittance is complementary to that of the absorption spectrum., so, around 290 nm is displayed as an absorbance band ascribable to the n - π^* electronic transition [25] induced by the non-bonding electrons [26]. Between 240 nm and 400 nm, there is an increase in transmission in pure PMMA, while at higher wavelengths it is stable, in agreement with the transparent nature of PMMA in the visible spectrum. In the composite is displayed the shift of the absorption to 290 nm and the decrease of the transmittance from 290 nm all along the visible range due to the presence of Pd structures.

Figure 3. Transmittance on foils of pristine PMMA, PMMA+1%Pd and PMMA+5%Pd foils.

The transmittance is decreased by about 62.5% in PMMA+1%Pd and by about 93,7% in PMMA+5%Pd as displayed in **Figure 3**.

A key property required of a good packaging material is the hydrophobicity to prevent fouling and contamination of food packages. An additional capability is the minimization of food waste and improving consumer experience due to the easy sliding of food from the inner side of the package [27]. **Figure 4** displays the contact angle measurements for both PMMA and Pd pristine, together with PMMA containing different concentrations of Pd.

Figure 4. Contact angle of PMMA pristine a), PMMA+5%Pd b) and PMMA+1%Pd c) composites and Pd pristine c).

The contact angle measurement shows that in the two composites, it increased by about 26% and 20%, with the increasing of the Pd percentage, leading to less hydrophilicity than pristine palladium.

The shore test D was performed on pristine PMMA and the composites. The tester shown in **Figure 5 a)** provided a value of about 58 shore [28] for the pristine PMMA while for the composites revealed an increase of about 37 % and 47% for PMMA+1%Pd and PMMA+5%Pd respectively. The increase in the hardness confirmed by the reduction of the mark diameter (see **Figure 5b)** is due to the presence of Pd nanopowder in the polymer matrix. The Pd nanopowder adequately restricts the indentation and consequently enhances the hardness of the composites.

Figure 5. Shore hardness tester a) and PMMA pristine, and PMMA+Pd composites.

In **Figure 5b)** are reported the optical images of the mark left of the surface of the samples. The circles with diameter decreasing from pristine PMMA to PMMA+1%Pd to PMMA+5%Pd respectively, are highlighted with red dotted line. The diameter (d) of the footprint is 0.186 mm for pristine PMMA, 0.128 mm for PMMA+1%Pd and 0.085 mm for PMMA+5%Pd in the three cases, respectively.

To obtain further information on the dynamic hardness and slipperiness of the polymer with and without Pd, scratch test measurements were carried out using a metallic tip with a weight of 3.6 g. The optical microscope photos of the grooves caused by the sliding demonstrate that the groove has a larger section in the case of pure PMMA, a smaller one in the case of PMMA+5%Pd and an intermediate one in the case of PMMA+1%Pd, confirming the shore hardness data reported above in static conditions. The scratch test figures are shown in **Fig. 6** together with those of a reference metallic wire that has a known diameter size of 97 μm . The scratch has a transversal size of 100 μm (a), 50 μm (b) and 20 μm (c) in pure PMMA, PMMA+1%Pd, and PMMA+5%Pd, respectively.

Figure 6. Scratch test measurements in pure PMMA (a), PMMA+1%Pd (b), and PMMA+5%Pd (c).

4. Discussion

In this study, polymeric composites were produced with different metallic filler concentrations for the production of efficient packaging material using recyclable and biocompatible materials: PMMA and Pd.

The decrease of the optical transmittance of about 62.5% in PMMA+1%Pd reflects a good attribute necessary for quality packaging to prolong the durability of food. The reduction of transmittance, but not opacity, makes possible an easy inspection of the wrapped products and at the same time preserves it from UV-VIS light absorption.

The wettability was investigated by means of contact angle measurements to monitor the hydrophobicity of the composites. The tendency of foods to interact with the packing affects the life of our products on shelves. This means that low hydrophilicity is desirable to assist the sliding of food from the inner side of the package [27] and avoid accumulation of water in contact with aliment, responsible for the degradation of food. The contact angle measured in PMMA+1%Pd displays better hydrophobicity than PMMA+5%Pd and pristine palladium due to the lower concentration of Pd making him more similar to pristine PMMA.

The shore hardness test indicated an improvement of the duration in the composites of about 37% in PMMA+1%Pd and 57% in PMMA+5%Pd due to the presence of the used filler.

The doping of PMMA with Pd enables the creation of hydrogen sensors, the modification of the material's resistance to oxidation and dechlorination processes and the modification of many physical and chemical properties of the polymer, such as optical, electrical, mechanical and chemical reactivity.

5. Conclusions

Food preservation can be referred to as the quality of the food, health, longer durability, and reduction of wasted food. Ensuring these benefits in the food chain system requires significant improvements in the quality of packaging materials.

This work can be considered a modest attempt at food safety and environmental protection by a simple modification of the PMMA properties for the manufacture of packaging material. The materials used in this study are PMMA and Pd, both recyclable and biocompatible.

The material used for the packaging should possess properties like transparency, flexibility, reduction of UV-VIS absorption, and hydrophobicity.

The original glass-like transparency of PMMA has been reduced with the increase of Pd concentration supporting the reduction of the UV-Vis component of light without inhibiting the identification of the packed item.

The study of other cheaper matrices and nanoparticles with proper features is being investigated for

a wider range of applications in the fields of chemistry, optics, mechanical, electrical, and biomaterial engineering.

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